

CRITICAL MATERIALS FOR AI: SECURING SUPPLY FOR THE TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION

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Abstract

The article explores the role of critical materials in the development of artificial intelligence infrastructure and in ensuring the resilience of technological innovation. It examines key elements – gallium, germanium, palladium, and neodymium – that determine the functioning of AI hardware components, including microchips, sensor systems, and magnetic modules. Based on data from the USGS, IEA, and industry reports, the study analyzes demand dynamics, production and processing capacities, and supply chain vulnerabilities. A scenario-based approach is proposed to assess the potential of the United States for localization and recycling of materials under varying rates of technological growth. The findings emphasize the need for systematic management of critical resources and diversification of supply sources as essential conditions for the sustainable development of the artificial intelligence industry.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, critical materials, rare earth elements, palladium, neodymium, supply chains, resilience.

Introduction

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) has become one of the key drivers accelerating technological transformation in the global economy. The growth of computing power, the exponential increase in data volumes, and the widespread adoption of energy-intensive machine learning models have led to a sharp rise in the demand for material resources essential to the functioning of AI infrastructure. At the core of this infrastructure lie critical materials – aluminum, silicon, copper, and a group of rare earth elements (gallium, germanium, palladium, and neodymium) – that enable the production of processors, cooling systems, high-performance computing nodes, and energy components of data centers. Compared to traditional sectors, the digital economy creates a peculiar pattern of material consumption whereby the overlap between high technological complexity and scarcity of resources amplifies the dependency of innovation systems on international supply chains.

At a moment of geopolitical divisions and concentrated production of rare materials in limited countries,

securing stable supply of critical materials has assumed strategic importance. Disruption in the supply of aluminum, copper, silicon, or rare earth elements can slow down national efforts to drive AI and microchip manufacturing. The relevance of this study is dictated by the need to analyze not only the size and dynamics of demand for these materials but also the capacity of national economies – first and foremost, that of the United States – to develop stable chains of production and recycling, reduce import dependence, and ensure long-term resource security for technological innovation.

Main part. The material basis of AI

Generally, AI development is progressively turning into an important economic driver of worldwide economic transformation – in the guise of growing compute power and data and infrastructure size required to support it [1]. According to a Boston Consulting Group (BCG) report, global data center demand for capacity is likely to grow at a rate of approximately 16% annually during the period of 2023–2028, significantly more than previous years' growth rates (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Global data center power requires to serve projected computing demand, GW [2]

AI infrastructure represents a complex system of hardware and energy networks whose functioning relies on both strategic and critical materials [3]. Materials include aluminum, silicon, and copper, which form the basis for structural, semiconductor, and conductive components of equipment. **Aluminum** is widely used

in the production of server casings, cooling system elements, and cable connections due to its high thermal conductivity and low density. **Silicon** serves as the primary material for manufacturing microchips and integrated circuits, while **copper** remains the key conduc-

tor of electricity and heat in power and data transmission systems. Together, these materials constitute the physical foundation of AI infrastructure, supporting higher technological layers – from graphics processors (GPU) to data centers. In accordance with a BloombergNEF report, demand for copper from companies that are implementing AI systems will average at about 400,000 metric tons annually for the next decade, with 572,000 tons in 2028.

According to U.S. Geological Survey categorization, gallium, germanium, palladium, and neodymium have been defined as critical materials that are extremely supply-vulnerable and of strategic importance to high-technology industries. These rare-earth and noble elements play a special role in the development of AI hardware solutions due to their unique physicochemical properties [4]. **Gallium and germanium** are used in the production of semiconductor heterostructures, infrared sensors, and lasers applied in machine vision systems and neural network accelerators. **Palladium** is indispensable in the manufacturing of multi-layer capacitors, contact elements, and catalysts, as well as in coatings and thin films that enhance the reliability of interconnections in microchips. **Neodymium** is employed in the creation of powerful permanent magnets for electric motors, drive and cooling systems, and data storage devices.

These materials ensure the stable and energy-efficient operation of high-performance computing systems, including GPU, neuromorphic processors, and quantum accelerators, which form the core of modern AI technologies. Collectively, strategic and critical materials constitute the material foundation of the digital era, defining the ultimate limits of performance growth, energy efficiency, and resilience of computing infrastructure.

Dynamics of demand for AI-related metals

The growth of computational workloads driven by the development of AI systems directly scales the demand for physical infrastructure, leading to increased consumption of both strategic and critical materials. One of the key elements of this infrastructure remains **copper** – the primary material used for power supply, wiring, and cooling systems. According to engineering assessments conducted at a real facility (the **Microsoft campus in Chicago**), copper intensity in such data centers reaches approximately 27 tons per megawatt (MW) of installed IT capacity. For so-called «AI hyperscale» facilities with high equipment density, this figure may be even higher, underscoring the dependence of AI infrastructure expansion on stable copper supply [5].

The role of copper is particularly evident at the microarchitectural level of modern computing devices. In 2024, Nvidia rolled out the GB200 NVL72 system with the Blackwell B200 GPU that has been classified as the most powerful chip globally. Estimates indicate that the new chip offers some four times the capability of its previous version, and up to 98% of the world's data center GPU market during 2023 was dominated by Nvidia. According to studies by BHP, the GB200 structure contains more than 5,000 copper wires with a total length of more than 3.2 kilometers, indicating the vast dependence of high-performance computing on copper and other conductive materials.

According to estimates by Rystad Energy, consolidated by the World Resources Institute (WRI), more than 100 gigawatts (GW) of new data center capacity will enter service in the United States during the period 2024-2035. To compare, it is roughly ten times bigger than the maximum summer load on New York's grid in 2023. Nevertheless, projections of future electricity consumption vary widely: according to various studies, by 2030, data centers may account for between 4.6 % and 9.1 % of total U.S. electricity demand [6]. This wide range is reflecting uncertainty regarding the build rate and potential supply constraints for some of the key infrastructure components, including transformers and distribution equipment.

According to London Economics, sustaining the projected growth rate of computing capacity in the United States will require purchasing up to 90 % of the world's semiconductor production over the next five years, creating significant pressure on global supply chains. At the same time, improvements in the energy efficiency of computing systems and advances in cooling technologies may partially offset the increase in power consumption, reducing the material intensity per unit of performance while maintaining the overall upward trend in cumulative demand for strategic and critical metals.

Demand for aluminum and silicon in the context of AI infrastructure development demonstrates a stable upward trend, reflecting the growth of computing capacity, the increasing number of data centers, and the expansion of semiconductor production. According to the Aluminum Association (2024), **aluminum** demand in North America, including the United States and Canada, increased by 4.6 % compared to the same period of the previous year, driven by the active development of digital and energy infrastructures (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Aluminum demand in North America (U.S. and Canada), million pounds [7]

These figures indicate the industry's recovery from a decline and establishment of a trend toward long-term growth based on building data centers and upgrading industrial machinery, where aluminum is utilized in cooling solutions, server enclosures, and cable solutions.

At the same time, the silicon wafer business that forms the foundation for making processors and graphics accelerators is also seeing a steady rise. The world silicon wafer market is expected to reach \$46.7 billion by 2033 (fig. 3), according to IMARC Group (2024).

Figure 3. Global silicon wafer market forecast, billion dollars [8]

All together, these symptoms confirm that although the material intensity per unit of computer capacity is slowly reducing due to technological miniaturization, the total demand for silicon and aluminum in America will increase with the development of AI infrastructure as well as that of the semiconductor industry.

Critical commodities such as **gallium, germanium, palladium, and neodymium** are noted by U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) reports to have low potential for expanding the capacity of production and high foreign trade restriction exposure. Particularly, 2023–2024 gallium and germanium mining was concentrated principally in China, which produces over 90 % of global production of these metals, and therefore the global availability is extremely vulnerable to the foreign policy of a nation. Since export licensure of gallium and germanium commenced in July 2023, global supply fell temporarily, and prices of germanium increased.

According to the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS, 2024), **palladium** production remains highly concentrated: its largest producers are Russia and South Africa, which together account for about 63 % of global production. This kind of manufacturing system is threatening supply chains for sophisticated electronics globally, including microchips, contacts, and catalysts, where palladium is used as a crucial material due to its high conductivity of electricity and corrosion resistance.

The International Energy Agency (IEA) reports that the demand for magnetic rare-earth elements like **neodymium** continues to grow with the rising production of electric motors, wind turbines, and electronics. By 2050, the total global demand for these elements will nearly double from the current levels, and if the existing production capacities are not altered, the shortage on the market is highly likely.

Thus, for palladium and neodymium – both essential to the hardware components of AI systems – factors of limited supply and rising demand persist, making

these materials strategically significant for the technological sector. Critical materials forming the foundation of AI hardware already represent a zone of resource vulnerability: highly concentrated mining, limited recycling capacity, and increasing demand from the AI industry reinforce the need for strategic supply planning and diversification of sources.

Scenario analysis of U.S. supply resilience for critical materials

The development of AI increases the dependence of the U.S. technological infrastructure on the supply of strategic and critical materials [9]. In the rare-earth segment, the production of **neodymium** magnets (NdFeB) plays a crucial role in electric motors, cooling systems, and quantum accelerators. In 2024, MP Materials resumed intermediate-stage processing of rare-earth concentrates, producing approximately 1,300 tons of neodymium–praseodymium (NdPr) oxide and increasing total concentrate output to about 45,000 tons – the highest level in recent years. Support from the U.S. Department of Defense has enabled the establishment of a full technological cycle – from extraction and separation to magnet production – which is expected to strengthen national self-sufficiency in the long term.

As noted earlier, according to USGS (2024), the leading producers of **palladium** remain Russia and South Africa, jointly accounting for about 63% of global output. Around 40 % of U.S. domestic demand is met through the recycling of automotive catalysts, which reduces the risk of supply shortages but does not eliminate price volatility. Similar risks apply to gallium and germanium: according to USGS Open-File Report 2024-1057, a complete halt in their exports from China could lead to a reduction in U.S. GDP of approximately \$3.4 billion, underscoring the strategic importance of these elements for high-technology sectors.

Taken together, these data make it possible to assess the strategic development scenarios of the U.S. critical materials sector amid the growing demand generated by the AI industry. To achieve a comprehensive understanding of the country's resource potential and vulnerabilities, three possible trajectories are considered – a baseline scenario reflecting gradual capacity expansion, an accelerated scenario involving industrial localization and rapid development of processing capabilities, and a resource-constrained scenario characterized by external risks and supply limitations (table 1).

Table 1.

Scenario analysis of U.S. supply security for critical materials essential to AI infrastructure

Material	Baseline scenario (2025–2030)	Accelerated scenario (industrial localization and technological expansion)	Resource-constrained scenario (geoeconomic risks and supply disruptions)
Gallium	Continued dependence on imports from China; limited recovery from by-product streams.	Development of secondary extraction technologies and pilot recycling facilities within the U.S.	Tightened Chinese export restrictions drive price surges and shortages in optoelectronic components.
Germanium	Limited domestic production; major imports from China and Canada.	Expansion of recycling and extraction from metallurgical residues; diversification of import sources.	Reduced exports from China cause declines in laser and infrared sensor production.
Palladium	Russia and South Africa jointly supply about 63% of global output; roughly 40% of U.S. demand met through recycling.	Increased investment in secondary recovery and substitution technologies; partial price stabilization.	Geopolitical instability and market volatility lead to supply disruptions in the electronics sector.
Neodymium (NdPr)	Department of Defense support enables NdPr oxide output (~1.3 kt in 2024) and gradual formation of a domestic magnet market.	Completion of the full production cycle «mining – separation – metal – magnets»; reduced dependence on China.	Delays in metal and magnet production; shortages of heavy rare-earth elements required for high-performance magnets.

The provided scenario analysis shows that the extent of U.S. resilience in guaranteeing the supply of strategic materials will heavily rely on the rate of localisation of production and processing capacities, as well as on the overall external economic situation. In the baseline scenario, the country increasingly solidifies its standing in several key sectors, i.e., the manufacturing of gallium, germanium, and palladium oxides of NdPr and developing recycling technologies while remaining dependent on imports of gallium, germanium, and palladium. The fast track scenario is distinguished by increased investment, creation of a whole cycle of technology, and diversification of supply, all of which together make up for the reduction of strategic risks and enhanced technological sovereignty.

In the case of supply restriction, the main risks remain the same: geopolitical tensions, price volatility, and potential supply disruptions from major producing regions. Overall, the results of the analysis bear witness to the need for systemic measures to encourage recycling, establish national stockpiles of critical materials, and forge international cooperation aimed at ensuring the secure functioning of the material foundation of AI facilities.

Conclusion

Development of AI is building a new structure of material dependency with hard-to-substitute and rare materials at the focus. Greater computer power and growing numbers of data centers are driving demand for critical materials that go into producing microchips,

sensor systems, and magnetic components. Despite technological advancements and efficiency improvements in energy usage, the cumulative material burden of infrastructure continues to increase, hence supply chain resiliency as a strategic factor in technology development. Critical materials have become core elements in the innovation system and access to them dictates the pace and scale of AI deployment directly.

For guaranteeing stability and continuity in metal cycles, a well-balanced system of processing, extraction, and recycling of rare metals has to be built. Developing domestic capabilities, refining recycling technologies, and diversifying sources are key to strengthening resource resilience, the research states. In the future, the ability to combine innovation in material science with systematic management of resource flows will determine national technological ecosystems' competitiveness and AI infrastructure sustainability amid growing global demand.

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